

Proton Ligand Formation Constants of 1-Amino-2-Naphthol-4-Sulphonic Acid (ANSA)

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Chelation tendency of 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid has been worked out and the proton ligand formation constants have been computed using various methods, in 50% aq.-dioxan, at 35° and at ionic strengths of 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M adjusted by the addition of KNO₃, with the use of Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique. Thermodynamic formation constants have been obtained by extrapolation to zero ionic strength.

METAL complexes have been reported to play an important part in the biological activity of drugs. A current theory of the drug action centres around the competitive binding¹. Further cancer formation and its inhibition, both involve chelation. The trace metals present in the body are generally transition metals. These abnormal metals change the behaviour of enzyme systems, by binding with them, and replacing the essential metals of these systems; they also change the structure of the nucleic acid by binding with them. Most of the compounds which cause cancer are also chelating agents. One of the several such compounds is 1-amino-2-naphthol-4-sulphonic acid. It is a purple coloured sparingly soluble compound in hot water. The structure of the molecule clearly indicates its potentiality for complex formation with metals. The amino-naphthols and their derivatives have been shown carcinogenic, particularly in the bladder cancer². Literature survey indicates that practically no work has been done with this compound describing its complex forming potentiality, except that with Pd(II) and V(V)³. Hence it was thought fruitful to work out the avidity of this molecule for chelate formation. As the molecule is an acid, its pK^a values will give an idea about the availability of the chelating species (the anion) at the physiological pH, 7.3. In this note, the proton ligand formation constants log K_{nH}^H, of ANSA have been calculated in 50% aq.-dioxan medium at 35° and at various ionic strengths with KNO₃. Thermodynamic formation constants have been obtained by extrapolation to zero ionic strength (Fig. 2).

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared by dissolving high purity chemicals in doubly distilled, CO₂ free water. ANSA (B. D. H.) was dissolved in dioxan, while KOH solution was prepared in CO₂-free water

and standardised against a standard solution of oxalic acid.

FIG-2

The Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique⁴, as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁵ was used to determine proton-ligand formation constants of ANSA. The two sets of solutions of (a) nitric acid and (b) nitric acid and ANSA, were prepared such that the total volume was 50 ml and the final concentrations were $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ HNO₃ and $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ ANSA in each case. The ionic strength of each of the solution was maintained at 0.05M, 0.1M and 0.2M using KNO₃. The titrant was 0.1M KOH and 'Systronics' pH-meter, No. 322, with a glass calomel electrode was used for the titrations.

From the titration curves the average number of proton associated with ANSA ($\bar{n}_A$) was calculated using the relation of Irving-Rossotti :

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \frac{(V''-V')(N^0 + E^0)}{(V^0 + V') \cdot TL}$$

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where, V' and V'' are the volumes of alkali required to reach the same pH in the acid and the ligand titrations curves respectively; while V^0 , TL^0 , E^0 and N^0 are the volume of the mixture, initial concentration of the ligand, initial concentration of the acid and the concentration of titrant respectively. Y is the number of dissociable protons.

From the values of $\bar{n}A$ at various pH values proton ligand formation constants, $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ were computed by various methods e.g., half integral, point-wise calculation and linear plot methods. The results obtained are recorded in Table 1. The proton-ligand formation curves at various ionic strengths are shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS, $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ OF ANSA AT 35°C AND AT VARIOUS IONIC CONCENTRATIONS

S. No.	Ionic concentration $KNO_3 : M$	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_n^H$	Method
1.	0.2	8.00	3.40	11.40	a
		7.93	3.35	11.28	b
		8.00	3.40	11.40	c
		8.00	3.40	11.40	
2.	0.1	7.80	3.25	11.05	a
		7.76	3.26	11.96	b
		7.80	3.25	11.05	c
		7.80	3.25	11.05	
3.	0.05	7.50	3.20	10.70	a
		7.40	3.15	10.63	b
		7.50	3.20	10.70	c
		7.50	3.20	10.70	
4.	0	7.20	3.05	10.25	

a. -Half $\bar{n}A$ method
b. -Pointwise Calculation Method
c. -Linear plot Method.

Fig. 1
— — — 0.2 M
○ — 0.1 M
— ○ — 0.05 M

pH -titration curve in case of the ligand showed two inflections one at $pH \sim 3.5$ and the other at $pH \sim 8$. The first one is associated with the removal of proton from $-SO_3H$ group while the second for the removal of the phenolic hydrogen. Thus the ionisation reaction may be represented as follows :

This indicates that at the physiological pH (7.3) the species available for the chelation will be-(II), which will react with trace metals ion of the body with the removal of the phenolic hydrogen in the following manner :

The stoichiometric studies of the chelates formed with the biologically active metals, $Mg(II)$, $Ca(II)$ and $Mn(II)$ and the carcinogenic metals, $Fe(III)$, $Al(III)$, $Cr(III)$, $Be(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Ni(II)$ and $Cu(II)$ were studied using conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations and applying monovariation method due to Nayar and Pande⁶ which indicated formation of two complexes, ML and ML_2 , in stepwise manner. Thus the final product with the divalent metal cation may be proposed to have the following structure. This clearly indicates that

most expected coordination number, six for the carcinogenic metal ions is not saturated completely at the physiological pH 7.3. This may favour the attachment of the chelates with the tissue and favour cancer formation.

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